

Blood feuds in Pakistan: A persistent challenge to peace and progress

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ABSTRACT: Blood feuds have been a persistent phenomenon of human history since the dawn of civilizations, transcending geographical, cultural, and temporal boundaries. This article encapsulates a comprehensive exploration of blood feuds, examining their origins, manifestations, and its impacts on Pakistan. and the socio-cultural factors that sustain and perpetuate it. The study will begin by examining the historical foundations of blood feuds and charting their development from prehistoric times to the present. Understanding the sociopolitical settings that have sparked these feuds will be emphasized, highlighting the significance of power relations, territorial disputes, and familial honor. An important component of this article will be examining the societal effects of blood feuds, including how they affect interpersonal relationships, judicial system, and communal structures of Pakistan. Additionally, the study will evaluate the efforts made by societies to lessen or end blood feuds, and how it would be helpful for Pakistan in order get rid of this plague, looking at both effective solutions and enduring problems.

The goal of this study is to further our understanding of blood feuds as intricate phenomena with wide-ranging effects. The study aims to present a comprehensive and complex picture of blood feuds by integrating historical, cultural, and societal viewpoints. This may help to generate insights that could guide conflict resolution and prevention tactics in modern communities and the ways to implicate these solutions in Pakistan.

Keywords: Blood Feuds, Familial Honor, Peace and Order, Human Rights

[Introduction](#)

[Historical Origin](#)

[Recommendations](#)

[Conclusion](#)

[References](#)

1. Introduction

Blood feuds are a type of violent conflict in which rival families or groups trade murders or injuries. Blood feud is feud between different clans or families (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2023). In many regions of the world, particularly in tribal civilizations with weak or nonexistent formal legal systems, blood feuds have a long history. Pakistan, a country with a diverse range of customs, traditions, and historical complexity, has a particular and pervasive social issue: the occurrence of blood feuds. These feuds, which go by the names

"Karakari"(Patel & Gadit, 2008) and "Swara," (Usafzai, 2004) have their origins in the complex network of tribal and familial ties that have molded the nation's social structure for generations. A culture of vengeance and retribution is perpetuated by blood feuds in Pakistan, which are defined by a cycle of revenge killings in which conflicts between families or clans turn into an apparently never-ending circle of bloodshed.

Blood feuds are still common in some rural parts of Pakistan, especially in the provinces of Sindh, Balochistan, and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and also in Punjab. These feuds, which can endure for decades, take many lives and disturb communal stability. They frequently result from disagreements over land, water, honour, or retaliation. Blood feuds have their origins in the old Pashtunwali code, an unwritten set of guidelines that control the conduct of Pashtun tribes in the region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Honour, (Shah, 2016) retaliation, and hospitality are highly valued in this code, which establishes a framework that protects communal honour while also encouraging a culture in which conflicts are frequently resolved by force. Blood feuds are still common in many parts of Pakistan because of the complex social structure and the dominance of patriarchal values.

The absence of strong state institutions and law enforcement is one of the things that makes blood feuds continue to exist in Pakistan. (Ijaz, 2017) Many residents of the nation's remote and underdeveloped areas turn to their own customary dispute resolution techniques because they lack faith in the government or the legal system to provide them with justice or safety. Jirgas, or tribal councils, are one of these techniques; they adjudicate disputes between parties and administer sanctions or recompense. Jirgas, however, are not always impartial or successful; on occasion, they may even make matters worse by enforcing unjust or harsh rulings. (Ahmed et al., 2021)

The availability of illegal firearms as well as the country's violent and macho cultures are other factors that contribute to blood feuds in Pakistan. Many people in the nation's conflict-ridden areas own guns, most of which are smuggled in from Iran or Afghanistan, and they use them to settle scores or show off their strength. It is also considered a mark of manhood and status to own and show weapons, and many young men are indoctrinated to participate in feuds as a means of upholding their honour and allegiance to their family or tribe. (Jafri, 2008)

The practice of "vani," or exchanging women or girls to settle disagreements, is another factor that contributes to the continuation of blood feuds in Pakistan. A young girl from one party is handed to a man from the other party in a situation known as "vani," (Hashmi & Koukab, 2004) which is a type of forced marriage used to put an end to a feud or make up for a loss. Vani violates the girl's human rights and dignity and frequently leads to her being abused and exploited without her consent. Vani is also a potential target for more hostility and violence since the girl's relatives might try to avenge her or get her back. (Khan, 2011)

Blood feuds are a major societal issue in Pakistan since they impede growth, hinder education, result in human rights violations, and cause deaths. The government and civil society have made some attempts to solve this problem, including outlawing the practise of vani, (Siddiqi, n.d.) keeping track of and documenting instances of blood feuds, and encouraging communication and peacemaking between the involved parties. To break the cycle of violence and bring peace and justice back to the impacted areas, additional work must be done as these initiatives have encountered numerous obstacles and constraints.

The purpose of this research is to examine the historical, cultural, and socioeconomic elements that have a role in Pakistan's ongoing blood feuds. We aim to comprehend the complex nature of this phenomenon and its effects on people's lives, communities, and the larger national landscape by delving into the complex dynamics of these feuds. This investigation will also consult academic literature, historical narratives,

and current news to offer a thorough understanding of the complexity related to blood feuds in Pakistan.

2. Historical Origin

Blood feuds were widespread in societies where family and blood ties served as the primary source of authority and where there was a lax rule of law (or where the state did not see itself as responsible for mediating this kind of feuds).

In increasingly centralized cultures where criminal law and law enforcement are in charge of punishing offenders, the practice has all but vanished. (United, 2000)

But unfortunately, in case of Pakistan, the nation still suffers from this plague and is still prevalent (Pakistan-Researched and Compiled by the Refugee Documentation Centre, 2009)

Pakistan's blood feud history is intricate and frequently linked to historical, tribal, and cultural elements. Blood feuds, referred to as "swara" or "vani" in some contexts, have been a persistent problem, especially in areas with strong tribal traditions and a high degree of customary practice influence. These conflicts frequently have their origins in regional traditions, familial honour, (Aase, 2017) and an ideal of justice that exists outside of the established legal system. Although giving a whole historical narrative is difficult, here are some aspects to consider.

Customary rules have played a significant role in the history of tribal societies in several parts of Pakistan, including Pashtunwali in the northwest. Blood feuds are frequently considered as a way to uphold honour and justice in these customary structures.

In certain areas, the customs of "vani" and "swara" entail the transfer of young girls as recompense between families in order to resolve conflicts. Even though they are forbidden, some communities continue to engage in these activities, which can cause protracted disputes.

Blood feuds can persist due to socioeconomic considerations such as poverty and limited access to formal legal systems. People may turn to conventional legal systems because they believe there are no other options.

Blood feuds are more common in Pakistani regions where there have been periods of conflict and militancy. These events can heighten tensions already present.

Causes of blood enmity:

Blood feuds can emerge due to various factors, including political conflicts, disputes over land and water rights, or other causes, with women (Goldstein, 2002) often becoming the primary targets of animosity. In this context, we will specifically explore blood feuds that revolve around issues related to land and women.

In July 2023, three people lost their lives in a violent altercation over land in the Alipur Chatta suburb of Brij Tasha village: a father, a son, and a nephew. During a continuing land dispute, the accused, Nauman alias Haider, shot and killed the victims, identified as Munawar, Iftikhar, and Saad Iftikhar. (Akram, 2023)

Another example is of murder over a portion of the house a brother killed his brother in October 2023, Wajid went there to settle a property dispute he had with his father Safdar, brothers Sohail and Bilal, and himself. (The Express Tribune, 2023)

According to information, Sohail shared the house with his father and spouse Mehwish. Bilal owned a portion of the home as well. Whether Wajid belonged to the inheritance was not immediately apparent. Wajid had married of his own free decision, the report said.

The rented-out upper part of the house was the subject of the dispute. Wajid desired to relocate there with his partner. But during the conversation between the brothers, things got heated. The complaint states that Sohail pulled out a gun and shot his brother.

In 1978, a Dutch scholar coined the term "honour killing" to distinguish these killings within families and communities from other forms of homicide. According to Carmen Quintanilla Barba, a member of C.E.E.O.W.M. (Committee on Equality between Women and Men), honour crimes are defined as "crimes committed as a result of the necessity to safeguard or preserve the family's honour." An honour killing is described as "an act of murder where an individual is slain due to their actual or perceived immoral conduct." (Sultana & Hussain, n.d.)

Honor killing is a conventional practice in the world and the situation of Pakistan is no different where it is exercised as a customary practice. (Churchill, 2018)

Illicit sexual relationships, as well as suspicions and speculations regarding them, are the primary concern among them. The dominant societal ideals of masculinity, known as *ghairat*, (Lari, n.d.) are the cause behind the punishment of killing in cases of illegal encounters, suspicions, and rumors of sexual violation. By misinterpreting Islam's prohibition on engaging in illegal sexual relations, it is exploited as justification for killing. The persistence of blood hostility is due to the formal legal system's inability to enforce its laws and it also varies with the geography although blood feuds are a national problem but their causes vary from culture to culture but one thing, they all share common that is woman and land nearly all of blood feuds are either because of women or land.

In the case of Akbar, the conviction for double murder under grave and sudden provocation, where a father killed his daughter and her paramour upon witnessing them engaged in illicit relations, was changed from section 302 (b) of the Pakistan Penal Code (PPC) to section 302 (c) of the PPC. The sentence of life imprisonment was subsequently reduced to 5 years of rigorous imprisonment. This legal development is documented in the Pakistan Law Journal 1997 Criminal Cases (Lahore) 899. (Govt. of The Punjab, 1997) and there are several other examples of sentence reduction under grave and sudden provocation. These kinds of judgments become case law and used in later incidents thus it takes out the element of deterrence in committing honour killings. It is important to note that the courts are considered as reflection of the mindset of the society and in case of honour killings it is quite clear but there are also numerous reforms by the govt. but the issue is the lack of implementation.

The way of dealing and justifying blood feuds is different in all province as tribal areas have more honor related feuds where Punjab has land related feuds.

This section delineates essential guidelines for engaging in blood feuds and illustrates them through case studies. According to local customs, if a man and a woman are caught in *flagrante delicto*, they may face execution, with no reprisals typically expected if both are killed simultaneously. It is imperative that they be promptly put to death together. However, if they are slain in different locations, there may be grounds for blood retaliation. (Chaudhary, n.d.-a) Similarly, retaliation may be pursued if the man's family denies the accusation. To exemplify, in the fields, Zafaran's sister and her lover were discovered together, prompting Zafaran's brothers to swiftly and simultaneously eliminate both. One of Zafaran's brothers claimed responsibility for killing them on the spot when he found his sister and her lover engaged in an intimate act, presenting himself to the authorities.

There were other stories told around the community that were not the same as the one the Zafaran family narrated. For instance, the man who was killed was the only son and came from an extremely low-income household. The Zafaran family did not want to cause a rift with that family, even though the affair was actually with another wealthy man. The town was aware of the issue, and this was an excellent opportunity to reestablish the *ghairat*, which can also mean manliness. Despite being accomplices, the Zafaran brothers sent their jobless youngest brother to admit to the assassination. In order to secure his release, the oldest brother—who had slain them—stayed in the background. In less than six months, the

two families had reached a peace agreement, and Zafaran's brother had been released.(Chaudhary, n.d.-b)

Blood retribution will undoubtedly begin if the male is the sole one killed following suspicions or rumors of an extramarital affair. The most frequent motive for assassinations is undoubtedly rumors of extramarital affairs. Even though the woman's family is certain of the two accused's chastity, they would nonetheless kill the guy because a rumour is worse than an unknown affair.

Ideals of Masculinity and Blood Enmity:

Women are perceived as the embodiment of men's honor, known as "ghairat." It is imperative to safeguard and regulate this ghairat to maintain adherence to masculine norms. Preserving the sexual integrity of women within one's family—whether they are mothers, wives, daughters, or sisters—is seen as crucial for upholding personal dignity.(Chaudhary, n.d.-c) The preferred scenario involves instilling enough fear in any man to deter them from even considering inappropriate interactions with a family member. Similarly, men are expected to assume a position of authority over women, remaining at home, displaying loyalty to their families and fellow men, and concealing their own sexuality. In essence, men should ideally avoid approaching women, even if approached, while women are not only expected to stay at home but also take measures to prevent unwanted advances from men.

Consequently, women who express their sexuality are considered equally responsible for jeopardizing the ghairat of the men in their family. Therefore, the restoration of ghairat typically requires the elimination of both the man and the woman, not just one of them, unless it becomes evident that only the man has transgressed the established boundaries and the woman has adhered to expected behavior.(Ali, 2001)This may explain why, on certain occasions, only men are subjected to lethal consequences.

A Pakistani mother was given the death penalty in January 2017 for burning her daughter alive and for getting married against her family's wishes, thereby "bringing shame to the family."(Reuters, 2017)

The gravest insult a man can receive is being labeled "baighairat," signifying a failure to manage and protect his wife or girlfriend and, consequently, dishonoring him. In fear of such dishonor, men may resort to punishing individuals merely suspected of engaging in sexual relations or those perceived as intending to do so. In these situations, unless it is confirmed that the women were also involved, there is no perceived necessity for the men to take the lives of their wives.

Masculine ideals dictate that retribution for such offenses should be sought by the deceased's family rather than involving the police. However, due to the inherent responsibility of the police to investigate homicide cases, the victims' relatives often opt for direct retribution rather than cooperating with law enforcement. Occasionally, jail is seen as a secure haven, prompting the killers, in adherence to notions of manliness, to voluntarily surrender to the police, particularly if both the man and woman are killed. The disparity between how men are expected to treat their own women and how they perceive the treatment of other men's women—or, at least, how they would prefer to—is a notable aspect of the ideal of masculinity.(Chaudhary, n.d.-c)

In Islamic doctrine, the concept of vicarious liability is absent, emphasizing that each individual is accountable for their own actions. The final sermon (Khutba Hijjah Tul Wida) of the Holy Prophet Muhammad (P.B.U.H.) explicitly states this principle, declaring that from that point forward, individuals are solely responsible for their offenses. The sermon further emphasizes that no son will be held accountable for the crimes of the father, and likewise, no father will be punished for the wrongdoings of the son. This underscores the Islamic belief in individual accountability and the separation of responsibility for one's actions from that of their family members.(Sultana & Hussain, n.d.)

Statistics:

The count of deliberate and illegal killings arising from violent conflicts over land resources, marital disagreements, intergang confrontations for territorial dominance or control, and predatory violence and killings orchestrated by armed organizations is estimated as intentional homicides. Not all intentional killings fall under the category of intentional murder; the differentiation often hinges on the method employed in carrying out the act. Homicides are typically committed by individuals or small groups, whereas killings in armed combat are usually executed by relatively cohesive organizations comprising several hundred members, and as a result, are frequently excluded from conventional homicide classifications. (Pakistan Murder/Homicide Rate 1990-2023, 2023)

- Pakistan murder/homicide rate for 2021 was 3.98, a 6.48% increase from 2020.
- Pakistan murder/homicide rate for 2020 was 3.74, a 2.34% increase from 2019.
- Pakistan murder/homicide rate for 2019 was 3.65, a 2.64% decline from 2018.
- Pakistan murder/homicide rate for 2018 was 3.75, a 1.45% decline from 2017.

Around 318 people were the victims of target killings. 384 cases of honour killings, and 4596 cases only in Punjab, 125 in Sindh, 3,345 in KPK, 177 in ICT, 89 in AJK, 62 in GB in 2022, states the human rights commission of Pakistan's annual report for 2022. Most of these cases being the result of blood feuds triggered over honour, land disputes etc. (Human Rights Commission of Pakistan, 2023)

Social impacts of Blood feuds:

Infringement of constitutional rights:

The constitution of Pakistan ensures its residents have access to certain fundamental rights. (THE CONSTITUTION OF THE ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF PAKISTAN NATIONAL ASSEMBLY OF PAKISTAN, 1973) A person's rights may have been violated in a number of ways when they are murdered. The following are some pertinent rights included in the Pakistani Constitution:

Right to Life (Article 9): According to Article 9 of the Pakistani Constitution, no one may be deprived of their life or liberty unless it is necessary to comply with the law. This basic right is blatantly violated by murder.

Right to a Fair Trial (Article 10-A): This article guarantees the right to a fair trial, which includes the rights to counsel and to be heard. A person is entitled to a fair and impartial trial if they are charged with murder.

Article 14: "Right to Dignity": This article safeguards each person's dignity, and murder is a grave transgression of that right.

Article 14: Freedom from Torture and Cruel, Inhuman, or humiliating Treatment: This article forbids the use of torture as well as any kind of cruel, inhuman, or humiliating treatment. This right would be violated if the murder included any kind of torture.

Right to Privacy (Article 14): Although not specifically stated in the Constitution, the Pakistani Supreme Court has affirmed the right to privacy as a basic freedom. The privacy of the deceased and their families may be affected in murder trials.

Article 25: Equality of Citizens: Article 25 of the Constitution of Pakistan underscores the principle of equality among citizens. According to this article, all citizens are considered equal before the law and are entitled to its equal protection. Notably, discrimination solely on the basis of sex is expressly prohibited by this constitutional provision. However, the article also acknowledges that the State retains the authority to enact special provisions aimed at safeguarding the rights and well-being of women and children and this right is also infringed in case of honor killing and other cases of blood feuds.

3. Recommendations

A broad, community-focused strategy is needed to prevent blood feuds. The creation of community-based mediation Programmes, which use professional mediators to guide discussions and agreements, is essential to this endeavor. These Programmes help resolve conflicts peacefully. Activists and activist groups from Pakistan and abroad are working to put an end to the practice, but some argue that real change won't occur until the public decides to denounce this practice. It is necessary to enact legislative reforms to fortify the legal system, guaranteeing a prompt and equitable settlement of disputes and deterring vigilante justice. A strong legal system plays a huge role in maintaining peace and preventing blood feuds, Pakistan strongly lacks in this field as conviction rate is only 5 to 10% max whereas in Japan it is 99%(Aronson, 2020) and it is considered as one of the most peaceful countries in the world and has the score 1.336 in global peace index and ranks 9th and Pakistan on the other hand has the score of 2.745 and ranks 146th in the world (Institute for Economics & Peace. Global peace index, 2023). Initiatives aimed at raising community awareness and promoting tolerance, resolving conflicts, and educating people about the negative effects of blood feuds are vital. Put in place educational initiatives that support peaceful cohabitation, tolerance, and dispute resolution abilities. Educate the masses about the legal ramifications of committing violent crimes. Education plays a key role in preventing blood feuds and countries with a high literacy rate does not face problems like blood feuds, Iceland is one of the world's safest countries and has a literacy rate of 99% whereas Pakistan has a literacy rate of 56.44%(Review, 2023) so it is clear that education plays a very key role in preventing crime. Understanding the value of cultural sensitivity, solutions should take into account regional customs and norms while tackling the underlying socioeconomic issues that fuel conflict, such as resource scarcity and poverty. Programmes for social and economic development are essential for raising standards of living and creating job opportunities. The trend is also observed that countries with higher GDP have a lower rate of homicides but there are a few exceptions like USA, All the countries with score less than 1.5 have per capita GDP of 35000 dollars(International, 2023). In order to treat the trauma and psychological impacts that sustain the cycle of retaliation, psychosocial support must be provided. A thorough and ongoing attempt to end the cycle of blood feuds involves the use of community policing, international assistance, restorative justice programmes, dialogue platforms, and early warning systems. In communities impacted by protracted wars, these actions together aim to build a foundation for enduring peace by encouraging a commitment to non-violence and peaceful cohabitation.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, blood feuds are a common occurrence in Pakistan and are a serious problem with wide-ranging effects on people, families, and communities. This long-standing custom, which has its roots in tribal and cultural standards, has shown to be a serious threat to social harmony and the rule of law. Long-lasting blood feuds not only cause deaths but also impede social and economic advancement, creating a vicious cycle of violence that is hard to escape. It will take a multifaceted strategy involving societal and legal actions to solve this difficult issue. Blood feuds can be lessened to a significant extent by legal system reforms that guarantee prompt and equitable justice as well as initiatives to inform communities about other means of conflict resolution. In addition, promoting awareness, education, and economic opportunities can help shift attitudes and end the cycle of retaliation and in order to establish comprehensive policies that address the underlying causes of blood feuds and foster a culture of reconciliation and peaceful conflict resolution, international organizations, non-governmental organizations, and the government must work together. Pakistan may advance towards a future where justice is administered

without the cycle of bloodshed that blood feuds perpetuate by cultivating a society that values human life over the continuation of old grudges. The only way Pakistan can expect to remove this deeply ingrained issue and clear the path for a more peaceful and forward-thinking society is via coordinated efforts on multiple fronts.

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